

THE PLACE OF HUMAN BEINGS IN SOCIETY IN ANTIQUE PHILOSOPHY

Abdunosirova Halima Erdllayevna

Associate Professor, Department of Social Sciences and Physical Culture,
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

Abstract. *This article analyzes the relationship between humans and society in ancient philosophy, as well as the role of humans in social life and issues of their moral and spiritual development. The ideas about humans, the state, and civil society put forward by ancient Greek thinkers are studied. In particular, the views of Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle regarding the significance of humans in societal development, their rights, and duties are examined. Furthermore, the importance of the legacy of ancient philosophy in the development of contemporary socio-philosophical thought is highlighted.*

Keywords: *ancient philosophy, human, society, state, citizen, ethics, spirituality, social relations, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, philosophical thought, ancient Greek civilization, social development.*

Introduction. In ancient times, Greece, considered the cradle of European culture, witnessed the formation of the first rational ideas about human social essence and the nature of human beings. The development of Greek philosophers' views on humans and society was significantly influenced by the Zoroastrian religious-philosophical teachings widely spread among the peoples of Central Asia. The unique natural climate and social conditions in ancient Greece facilitated the advancement of science and philosophy. Across this region, various philosophical schools emerged, analyzing the problems of the universe and humans from different perspectives. One of these schools was the Milesian school. Among its philosophers, Thales (circa 624-547 yy.) was one of the first to put forward ideas

in human history that a person could “understand oneself,” that “everything should be in measure” in human activity, and that changes in the universe and in humans could be comprehended by human intellect and reasoning, without invoking unknowable gods or spirits [1]. His student, Anaximander (circa 610-547/546 yy), hypothesized that humans originated from aquatic creatures. It is known that by the 5th century BCE, democratic systems had been established in many Greek cities. The growing participation of humans in state affairs required continuous improvement of eloquence, mastery in the art of persuasion, and the ability to influence others effectively.

In various philosophical doctrines, these issues have been interpreted differently. Human beings, as social, historical, and cultural entities, strive in every era to gain a deeper understanding of themselves and to realize their true human essence. The wise words of the ancient philosopher Socrates, “Know thyself, human”, continue to acquire new significance in every historical period. The great thinker Abduholiq Gijduvani did not consider humans to be mere small worlds without purpose. This is because, in the ideas of Islam, it is emphasized that the universe was created primarily for humans. Humans, created in the world, gradually discovered human qualities within themselves as a biological species. A human is the most complex being in the world, embodying biological, social, and spiritual characteristics - an advanced product of nature, a conscious entity. In this way, communities of fully developed humans first formed groups and later created societies.

The emergence of society and the basis on which social relations are organized have always attracted the interest of the scientific community. Society has been defined as follows: it is a relatively stable association of individuals who possess speech, knowledge, and experience, based on the division of social labor, and who require mutual assistance and support. Considering that human society arose on the basis of mutual aid and support, there is no doubt that humans are also united by

direct spiritual factors.

As noted above, the object of the philosophy of society and humans is the research conducted on society and human beings, the development of philosophical thought, and the role of humans in society. Its subject, of course, is the range of problems related to societal development and human life, the issues that have yet to be studied, and the philosophical reflection these problems demand. Currently, the primary focus of philosophy remains the problems of humans, because questions about the meaning of human life, existence, non-existence, and human challenges are increasing year by year. Forces capable of fundamentally transforming the human spiritual world are emerging. Therefore, the subject of the course on the philosophy of society and humans is constituted by these contemporary, urgent, and multidimensional problems.

Humans have always strived to know their identity and self. Various hypotheses, theories, and concepts have been developed to address the problem of human existence. However, as time passed, previously unknown and unresolved issues concerning the being called “human” continued to multiply. Representatives of ancient philosophy, particularly philosophers from Ancient India and China, understood humans as consisting of two major powers: the body and the soul. According to them, the soul separates from the body and becomes a spirit, which is immortal. Meanwhile, philosophers from Ancient Iran and Turan viewed human existence and the existence of the universe as directly interconnected, considering the four fundamental elements of the universe as integral to human existence.

Contemporary philosophical sciences are divided into approximately twenty streams to analyze these issues. All of them primarily focus on the essence of humans, their nature, and their place in society. According to these doctrines, analyzing the essence of humans must also take into account the demands of contemporary civilizational values. Humans are the most extraordinary and unique beings among living creatures on Earth, capable of self-awareness and self-

governance. They are also beings who value their own life and struggle to understand the meaning of their existence.

In ancient Greece, once citizens began participating in state affairs, there arose a need for individuals who could speak eloquently, engage in debates, and possess comprehensive knowledge. In response to these demands, the philosophical movement of the Sophists emerged. According to the Sophists (teachers of wisdom), humans must observe all phenomena and events in the surrounding world critically, repeatedly examining their reflections and thoughts about the universe. In other words, any assertion, belief, or conviction accepted superficially or without scrutiny must be periodically tested and critically assessed.

The Sophists played a positive role in the development of Hellenic culture. As theorists of the art of rhetoric, they placed great emphasis on the power of speech, and many of them were exceptional orators. Their contributions to the field of logic were also significant. At a time when the laws of logic had not yet been formally established, the Sophists helped create the conditions for the discovery of the principles of reasoning. In philosophy, they primarily focused on issues related to humans, society, and knowledge [2].

From the reflections of the Sophists on societal and human moral development, several conclusions can be drawn:

The most important traits expressing humaneness—such as goodness, benevolence, kindness, justice, and other moral virtues—were evaluated from the perspectives of relativism and subjectivism;

Humans were considered capable of influencing any form of existence;

It is always necessary to take into account the unique characteristics of human existence and to recognize its distinctiveness [3].

The extraverted and introverted aspects of self-knowledge are vividly reflected in Heraclitus' views. According to him, one cannot comprehend the secrets of nature without first understanding the secret of the self. To know reality and

understand its significance, one must make an effort to understand oneself [4].

Among the reflections on human existence in Ancient Greek philosophy, the ideas of Socrates are particularly commendable. By acknowledging that the study of the human problem is the central task of philosophy, Socrates went significantly beyond the philosophical views of his contemporaries. He emphasized: “A person who seeks to change others must first change himself” [4, p. 66]. This call by Socrates expresses the essence of his moral philosophy. In his view, human beings are not separated from existence; they are sustained by a divine force surrounding them. The human being is not a passive object but is endowed with creative inquiry and the ability to transform the existing order and environment.

According to Plato, humans are created by a divine power. In other words, in Plato’s view, the same divine force is directly connected with the universal worldly soul, which also relates to the being called a human. The individual human soul is a reflection, a vibration, of this universal soul. The gods, in turn, are nothing other than ideas endowed with life and animation. Plato analyzes each person’s soul within the context of the interconnection between humans and society. According to his explanation, a human being can never satisfy their needs alone. Therefore, humans always feel the necessity to act collectively and collaboratively within a community.

Social life imposes specific demands on every individual. To meet these demands, certain social virtues and qualities are necessary. Plato emphasized that these virtues and qualities required by humans are not innate; rather, they are cultivated through education and upbringing. In reflecting on human social virtues and qualities and their place in society, Plato put forward a series of ideas concerning the division of labor and human participation in work.

Aristotle, in turn, highlighted the decisive role of society in elevating humans to the status of true human beings. Humans are formed as moral beings only within society. However, such cultivation can occur only under the conditions of a just

state. Achieving the supremacy of laws created on the principles and norms of true justice, and ensuring their enforcement, fosters genuine human virtues among citizens. Aristotle was among the first to introduce the concept of “civil society” into philosophy, thereby creating social and political values relevant to his era and for generations to come.

Conclusion. The views of Ancient Greek philosophy on human beings and society are of great significance due to their diversity. Many of these thinkers interpreted the human being as a part of the cosmos, a kind of microcosm embodying certain unique characteristics. Ancient Greek philosophers did not doubt that there is a fundamental distinction between humans and other living beings. The attempt to prove that humans are rational animals and political beings, as well as the recognition of the relationship between human ways of life and rational thinking, testify to the great contribution of Greek philosophical culture to the development of world civilization.

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